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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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TABLE OF CONTENT

Lists of tables and figures	3
List of abbreviations	3
I. INTRODUCTION	4
A. Context and purpose of the work	4
B. The technology intelligence-based approach for this work	5
C. Main findings and possible further developments.	6
II. METHODOLOGY	7
A. Data collection	8
B. Data cleaning and processing	9
C. Impact on the analysis process	11
III. IDENTIFICATION OF POINTS OF SYNERGY	12
A. Global volumetry and dynamic	12
B. SDG contribution <i>to identify similarities related to R&I topic</i>	13
C. Direct collaboration between ENLIGHT members <i>to identify similarities related to R&I topic</i>	18
D. Indirect collaborations <i>to identify similarities related to the existing R&I network</i>	20
IV. INDIVIDUAL PROFILES FOR ENLIGHT MEMBERS	25
A. University of the Basque Country	26
B. University of Bordeaux	27
C. Comenius University Bratislava	28
D. University of Galway	29
E. Ghent University	30
F. University of Göttingen	31
G. University of Groningen	32
H. University of Tartu	33
I. Uppsala University	34
V. APPENDIX	35
A. Global S&T data	35
B. Global organization characterization data	35
C. Individual data per university	35

Lists of tables and figures

Figure 1 Data collection, cleaning and processing process	7
Figure 2 Collected data and exploitable data for the 3 types of data regarding SDG mapping	10
Figure 3 Typology of organizations and related number of categorized organizations	11
Figure 4 Volume of S&T data per ENLIGHT university regarding the 3 types of S&T data	13
Figure 5 Temporal distribution regarding the 3 types of S&T data	13
Figure 6 Total SDG contribution for ENLIGHT + link SDG description	14
Figure 7 SDG contribution for ENLIGHT by university	15
Figure 8 Collective and specific contribution to SDG per university based on SciPub	16
Figure 9 Collective and specific contribution to SDG per university based on ResPro	17
Figure 10 SDG' collective and specific contributions synthesis	17
Figure 11 Collaborations between ENLIGHT universities on FamPat / ResPro	18
Figure 12 Collaborations between ENLIGHT universities on ResPro and associated SDG	19
Figure 13 ENLIGHT collaboration network based on FamPat	21
Figure 14 Transversal partners based on FamPat	22
Figure 15 ENLIGHT collaboration network based on ResPro	23
Figure 16 Key partners based on ResPro	24

List of abbreviations

S&T	Scientific and technological
R&I	Research and Innovation
NFPO	Non-for-profit organizations
FPO	For profit organizations
FamPat	Patent family
SciPub	Scientific publication
ResPro	Research project
IPC	International patent classification
CPC	Cooperative patent classification
SDG	Sustainable development goals

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Context and purpose of the work

ENLIGHT is a European university alliance willing to promote equitable quality of life, sustainability and global engagement through higher education transformation. ENLIGHT brings together nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries.

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society (SwafS) work programme. The ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for SociEty) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT alliance. In synergy with ENLIGHT's educational components and surrounding ecosystems, ENLIGHT RISE will deploy a comprehensive joint transformation agenda for our universities.

The main objective of Work Package 2 (WP2) of ENLIGHT RISE is to create synergies through R&I capacity building and to contribute to establish a common Research & Innovation agenda. Complementing the mapping of expertise in the ENLIGHT Think Tank (Erasmus+), WP2 analyses the alliance members' scientific and technological profiles to identify the strongest research synergies leading to maximize ENLIGHT alliance's competitive advantage (task 2.1). WP2 Research & Innovation observatory will help identifying ENLIGHT R&I capacities (task 2.2) and R&I synergies will be established through focus groups and incentives mechanisms (task 2.3).

This document represents deliverable D2.1. It explores and applies a technology intelligence-based approach to map the R&I activities of the nine universities of the alliance based on a set of selected scientific and technological data associated with them.

Research & Innovation synergies identified at this "macroscopic" level will assist the ENLIGHT governance in identifying R&I areas where the alliance is most competitive internationally. It will also provide the Research & Innovation support group with broad orientations for prioritizing R&I support activities (WP1).

B. The technology intelligence-based approach for this work

Technological intelligence can be defined as all coordinated activities aimed at acquiring solid knowledge of the scientific and technological environment to support the decision-making process, related to management of Research & Innovation.

In the case of the ENLIGHT alliance, the main objective was to help identify and create R&I synergies between the 9 members of the ENLIGHT alliance.

Therefore, to address this issue, *exploring* and *applying* a data-driven workflow according to the following approach was suggested:

Collecting, processing and analysing specific S&T data related to the 9 members of the alliance to help understand R&I activities at the ENLIGHT scale and identify similarities between its members.

Precise points of similarity have been targeted:

1. Similarity related to R&I topic existing in each of the universities of the alliance.
2. Similarity related to the existing network of partners at each university of the alliance.

To observe these points of similarity, the work relied on the usage of data that allowed to *read* and *understand* R&I activities regarding the 9 members of the alliance.

3 types of data have been selected for this purpose:

- **Patents data** (*FamPat*)
- **Scientific publications data** (*SciPub*)
- **Funded research projects data** (*ResPro*)

Note that this mapping is to be considered as a first work of applied exploration which aims to provide a broad appreciation of the existing R&I dynamics within the ENLIGHT alliance.

It already offers the first elements of actionable knowledge but also paves the way for future improvements and developments to strengthen the ability of the ENLIGHT alliance to better understand its R&I dynamics.

C. Main findings and possible further developments.

1. **Similarities related to R&I topic: *Identify similar position between the 9 universities regarding their individual contribution to R&I topics.***
 - [SDG 3](#) and [SDG 9](#) show *similar specific positions* across the 9 ENLIGHT universities on the SciPub as on the ResPro.
 - *Similar specific positions* according to the type of data should also be noted:
 - SciPub data: [SDG 10](#)
 - ResPro data: [SDG 4](#), [SDG 7](#), [SDG 8](#), [SDG 13](#).
 - [SDG 1](#), [SDG 5](#), [SDG 6](#), [SDG 14](#), do not show *individual specific position* on any type of data.
 - To address future investigation within the ENLIGHT framework related to specific SDGs, some groups of universities might be considered as *possible thematic cluster* as they already share significant collaborations on some SDGs:
 - [SDG 3](#): Ghent University // University of Groningen // Uppsala University // University of Tartu
 - [SDG 4](#): Ghent University // University of Tartu
 - [SDG 8](#): University of Groningen // University of Bordeaux // Ghent University // University of Göttingen // Uppsala University
 - [SDG 9](#): University of Groningen // Ghent University // University of Bordeaux // University of Tartu
 - [SDG 12](#): University of Groningen // University of Bordeaux
 - [SDG 13](#): Ghent University // University of Groningen // University of Galway // Uppsala University
 - Further developments might involve:
 - Deeper analysis on specific SDGs of interest.
 - Deeper analysis of the FamPat data using technological codes.
 - Complementary analysis using alternative methods to mapped SDGs.
 - Complementary analysis using alternative framework than SDGs.

2. **Similarities related to the existing R&I network: *Identify shared R&I' partners between the 9 universities of the alliance.***
 - Different types of partners have been identified:
 - *Key partner (KP)*: An organization that already collaborates with all 9 universities of ENLIGHT.
 - *Transversal partner (TP)*: An organization that already collaborates with 2 to 8 of the 9 universities.
 - *Specific partner (SP)*: An organization that already collaborates with only one of the 9 universities.
 - Depending on the type of data, the distribution between those 3 types of partners changes:
 - Identified partners on FamPat: No *key partners* / 4% are *transversal partners* / 96% are *specific partners*.
 - Identified partners on ResPro: 7% are *key partners* / 70% are *transversal partners* / 23% are *specific partners*.
 - Organizations have also been characterizing according 2 types: *For-Profit-Organizations* // *Non-For-Profit-Organizations*.
 - List of *key partners (KP)*, *transversal partners (TP)* and *specific partners (SP)* is accessible as restricted access document via the appendix.
 - Further developments might involve investigation on specific profile of partners using the created typology.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodology regarding the *collection*, *cleaning* and *processing* of the selected S&T data can be summarize with the following chart and is detailed in the following section.

Figure 1 Data collection, cleaning and processing process

A. Data collection

Data was collected from two main databases:

1. **FamPat** and **SciPub** data were collected from the [LENS.ORG](#) database.
2. **ResPro** data was collected from the [CORDIS](#) database.

These two databases were selected based on the cost associated with the usage of data.

[CORDIS](#) and [LENS.ORG](#) are *free to use* databases which allowed the collection and usage of the data necessary for the current task to be accomplished.

SCOPE OF QUERIES REGARDING THE 3 TYPES OF S&T DATA

FamPat data:

- No temporal limitation.
- Unit is [simple family](#) as defined in the LENS.ORG database.

Scientific publications:

- Limited to scientific articles with *publication date* between 2016 and 2021.
- Unit is *scientific articles* according to the typology of scientific outputs made available by the [LENS.ORG](#) database.

Funded research project:

- FP7 and H2020 projects available on [CORDIS](#) database.

QUERIES

Regarding the 3 types of data and following the conditions mentioned above, queries associated with each of the 9 universities of the ENLIGHT alliance were built.

The objective was to collect the most *complete* and *representative* corpus of data possible for each university.

The selected approach relies on textual queries applied to the *name of the applicant organizations* (FamPat data), the *name of the author's affiliation* (SciPub data) and the *name of the institution involved in the project* (ResPro data).

In addition to this approach, in the case of FamPat and SciPub data, the [LENS.ORG's affiliation search tool](#) was used to complete certain queries.

This results in the collection of **27 datasets** corresponding to the **3 types of data** for each of the **9 universities**.

In total, **3,057 FamPat**, **210,043 SciPub** and **3,003 ResPro** were collected corresponding to the 3 *raw datasets*.

FamPat and SciPub data that were collected for this work are available directly via the [LENS.ORG](#) database to be accessed and explored.

See [appendix](#) to explore full *Structured Datasets* used for the work.

ENLIGHT UNIVERSITY	FamPat Collection	SciPub Collection
University of the Basque Country	Patent - Lens Collection	Articles - Lens Collection
University of Bordeaux	Patent - Lens Collection	Articles - Lens Collection
Comenius University Bratislava	Patent - Lens Collection	Articles - Lens Collection
University of Galway	Patent - Lens Collection	Articles - Lens Collection
Ghent University	Patent - Lens Collection	Articles - Lens Collection
University of Göttingen	Patent - Lens Collection	Articles - Lens Collection
University of Groningen	Patent - Lens Collection	Articles - Lens Collection
University of Tartu	Patent - Lens Collection	Articles - Lens Collection
Uppsala University	Patent - Lens Collection	Articles - Lens Collection

B. Data cleaning and processing

1. CLEANING STEP

A cleaning work of the *affiliation's name* associated FamPat, SciPub and ResPro was carried out according to the following process:

- Grouping rules were created for the *raw SciPub dataset*. The grouping rules make it possible to group affiliations corresponding to the same organizations but written differently.
- The grouping rules created on the *raw SciPub dataset* were taken and adapted to be applied to the *raw FamPat dataset* and *raw ResPro dataset*.

2. PROCESSING STEP

Sustainable Development Goals mapping

The grid provided by the [17 Sustainable Goals Development – SDG](#) offers a reliable and readable blueprint to understand and characterize priority topics in the S&T data. Also, SDGs can be linked to the [5 flagship challenges](#) that has been selected as priorities by the ENLIGHT alliance. For those two reasons, the SDGs blueprint was selected as the main framework to identify the similarities in terms of topics.

As the SDG contribution is not filled originally in the S&T data used for this work, a dedicated process to associate the SDGs with the data was carried out. In this report, this work about SDG mapping relies on the use of the [SDG MAPPER](#).

Depending on the type of data, the available information associated with descriptive fields/variables could vary from one data entry to another. This had an impact on the calculation of additional data on incomplete or absent fields like SDG mapping or topics extraction.

Also, the SDG mapping matched differently depending on the type of data. This has methodological implications that will be expose in a [following section](#).

	FamPat		SciPub		ResPro	
TOTAL COLLECTED	3,057	100%	210,043	100%	3,003	100%
EXPLOITABLE DATA FOR SDG MAPPING <i>Data including abstract</i>	2,056	67%	172,528	82%	3,003	100%
DATA CATAGORIZED WITH AT LEAST ONE SDG share on EXPLOITABLE DATA FOR SDG MAPPING	89	4%	33,523	19%	1,584	53%

Figure 2 Collected data and exploitable data for the 3 types of data regarding SDG mapping

In addition to using SDGs, a complementary work involving extraction of specific data dedicated to topics in the individual profiles of the 9 universities was conducted: “*Topics*” were extracted based on the FamPat, “*Field of Study*” field directly available in LENS.ORG for SciPub and the “[EuroSciVoc](#)” field is directly available in CORDIS for ResPro.

Characterization of Organizations

Following the cleaning step, *characterization of the organizations* was carried out to create to typologies:

Typology 1

- **FPO (For-Profit Organization):** Corresponds to organizations with a private company profile.
- **NFPO (Non-For-Profit Organization):** Corresponds to organizations not classified as a FPO, e.g. public research institutions, government institutions, professional associations, social associations, etc.

Typology 2

- **Key partner (KP):** An organization that already collaborate with all 9 universities of ENLIGHT.
- **Transversal partner (TP):** An organization that already collaborate with 2 to 8 of the 9 universities.
- **Specific partner (SP):** An organization that already collaborate with only one of the 9 universities.

FPO / NFPO	Number of categorized organizations
FPO	942
NFPO	91820
TOTAL	92762
KP / TP / SP	
KP FamPat	0
TP FamPat	55
SP FamPat	1495
TOTAL FamPat Partners	1550
KP SciPub	1277
TP SciPub	13364
SP SciPub	57846
TOTAL SciPub Partners	72487
KP ResPro	185
TP ResPro	1894
SP ResPro	618
TOTAL ResPro Partners	2697

Figure 3 Typology of organizations and related number of categorized organizations

C. Impact on the analysis process

Differentiated uses of data according to the similarity dimensions.

The SDG mapping and characterization of organizations steps lead to consider differentiated uses of the 3 types of data analysed according to the objectives of the work:

Specific types of data have been used to work on specific similarity dimensions:

1. Similarities related to R&I topic: **ResPro data + SciPub data**
2. Similarities related to existing network of partners of each university of the alliance: **FamPat data + ResPro data**

These choices were based on the following observations and conclusions:

FamPat

- Using FamPats to understand topics from universities' portfolio should be completed by using technological codes ([IPC](#), [CPC](#)) available on FamPats. Within the scope of this project, we could not carry out such a task.
- SDG mapping on FamPat shows limits related to the vocabulary used in FamPat (technical solution to a technical problem) and should be refined to better use this type of data. Within the scope of this work, carrying out such a task was not possible.
- Affiliations on the same FamPat can be considered as effective to analyse the existing partner networks.

SciPub

- In this work, using SciPub to understand topics from universities' portfolio is relevant but comes up against the ability to map SDGs from this data: 19% of available SciPub data was matched with at least one SDG. SciPub data can therefore be used with caution as SDG mapping covers a limited shares of the SciPub.
- The complementary usage of "Fields of study" will then be interesting on individual profiles.
- Affiliations on the same SciPub record, although showing a collaborative work, has limits. Indeed, the nature of certain works associated with SciPub implies a very large number of researchers to be presents on some SciPub. This can limit the effective nature of the collaboration observed between the affiliations.

ResPro

- As 53% of all ResPro records was matched with at least one SDG, the SDG mapping offered usable results to analyse similarities related to R&I topic.
- ResPro data is also relevant to identify similar partners in the existing collaboration networks as by nature a lot of EU funded project involved direct collaboration between the project's members.

III. IDENTIFICATION OF POINTS OF SYNERGY

A. Global volumetry and dynamic

There is a heterogeneous distribution in terms of size of S&T portfolios between the 9 universities of the alliance (see figure 4)

The overall FamPat volume relates to the activity of filing patents which is in turn highly impacted by the individual university's strategy of promoting the products of R&I. Representative examples of that being the University of Uppsala which cedes patent ownership to researchers and is therefore not listed as patent applicant itself, whereas the universities of Ghent and Bordeaux show important patent portfolios (1,018 FamPat and 680 FamPat) compared to the average size of the patent portfolio (340 patent families).

	NB FamPat	NB SciPub	NB ResPro
University of the Basque Country	310	21,200	331
University of Bordeaux	680	25,157	208
Comenius University Bratislava	112	7,795	57
University of Galway	260	9,747	338
Ghent University	1,018	39,509	644
University of Göttingen	260	24,543	244
University of Groningen	325	38,496	604
University of Tartu	96	8,381	283
Uppsala University	7	40,807	539

Figure 4 Volume of S&T data per ENLIGHT university regarding the 3 types of S&T data

Temporal distribution is also heterogeneous but however, there has been an overall and steady increase in SciPub and ResPro in recent years at the ENLIGHT scale. This has to be compared to individual dynamics by university (see individual [profiles section](#)).

Figure 5 Temporal distribution regarding the 3 types of S&T data

B. SDG contribution to identify similarities related to R&I topic

The overall contribution of ENLIGHT to the [17 existing SDGs](#) differs according to the type of data but there is nevertheless noticeable information:

- [SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being](#) is the most relevant SDG in the global corpus and at the individual scale in each of the universities of the alliance (see table 9).

- The 2nd most prevalent SDG is [SDG 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure](#) which is important in all universities, particularly on ResPro data.
- [SDG 10: Reduced Inequality](#), [SDG 13: Climate Action](#), [SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy](#) is also highly represented but with different distribution regarding type of S&T data and universities.

Figure 6 Total SDG contribution for ENLIGHT + link SDG description

		SDG 1	SDG 2	SDG 3	SDG 4	SDG 5	SDG 6	SDG 7	SDG 8	SDG 9	SDG 10	SDG 11	SDG 12	SDG 13	SDG 14	SDG 15	SDG 16	SDG 17
University of the Basque Country	SciPub	58	102	976	248	74	66	214	139	445	334	115	183	167	49	181	125	36
	ResPro	6	8	14	20	3	7	21	18	53	8	11	13	28	6	13	5	9
University of Bordeaux	SciPub	51	136	1,753	89	20	70	78	99	350	345	65	120	197	69	181	75	48
	ResPro	3	1	28	10	1	1	15	13	35	4	4	6	9	2	1	2	3
Comenius University Bratislava	SciPub	24	50	529	39	17	33	23	61	115	106	37	28	43	5	64	49	20
	ResPro	-	-	4	2	1	-	1	4	11	2	4	1	3	-	2	4	3
University of Galway	SciPub	63	83	974	174	24	88	84	67	206	141	29	58	102	77	93	60	27
	ResPro	7	11	28	28	1	4	22	23	71	8	6	12	25	10	8	8	12
Ghent University	SciPub	167	464	2,652	327	91	252	259	243	764	639	197	285	387	115	531	181	81
	ResPro	9	35	87	32	2	18	51	45	89	18	23	57	39	9	31	13	21
University of Göttingen	SciPub	109	347	1,082	106	35	92	88	181	365	365	81	188	322	30	686	118	40
	ResPro	4	10	15	12	2	2	10	10	46	5	2	7	12	-	11	5	4
University of Groningen	SciPub	161	271	3,926	305	65	74	208	335	710	683	154	154	297	66	169	175	47
	ResPro	10	8	89	28	5	2	30	33	76	16	23	16	22	3	8	14	14
University of Tartu	SciPub	26	57	567	79	9	47	37	60	153	132	40	36	132	63	189	52	10
	ResPro	9	3	51	23	1	9	8	23	57	9	14	9	14	4	13	8	10
Uppsala University	SciPub	164	530	3,129	197	102	226	319	248	524	499	172	234	568	88	671	188	46
	ResPro	10	4	67	22	4	6	42	25	97	18	15	27	31	4	14	9	6

Figure 7 SDG contribution for ENLIGHT by university

A “specific position” on one SDG for one university means that its contribution to this SDG is higher than its average contribution on the 17 SDGs.

Defining *specific position* this way helps to identify *similar specific positions* at the ENLIGHT alliance scale.

On the other hand, some SDGs show *no specific positions*. This does not imply that the universities of the ENLIGHT alliance do not have contribution to the related SDGs, it implies that their contribution to those SDGs is below their average contributions to the other SDGs.

On SciPub data,

- The SDGs with *similar specific positions* are [SDG 3](#), [SDG 9](#) and [SDG 10](#). All the 9 universities of the ENLIGHT alliance have *specific individual position* of their SciPub on these 3 SDGs.
- [SDG 2](#), [SDG 4](#), [SDG 7](#), [SDG 13](#) and [SDG 15](#) show specific but not collective positions.
 - [SDG 2](#): Uppsala University // University of Göttingen // Ghent University
 - [SDG 4](#): University of the Basque Country // University of Galway
 - [SDG 7](#): University of the Basque Country
 - [SDG 13](#): University of Tartu // Uppsala University // University of Göttingen
 - [SDG 15](#): University of Tartu // Uppsala University // University of Göttingen // Ghent University
- [SDG 1](#), [SDG 5](#), [SDG 6](#), [SDG 8](#), [SDG 11](#), [SDG 12](#), [SDG 14](#), [SDG 16](#) and [SDG 17](#) do not show individual specific position.

Figure 8 Collective and specific contribution to SDG per university based on SciPub

On ResPro data,

- SDGs with similar specific positions on ResPro are [SDG 3](#), [SDG 4](#), [SDG 7](#), [SDG 8](#), [SDG 9](#), [SDG 13](#). There are at least 7 alliance universities on these SDGs.
- [SDG 2](#), [SDG 11](#), [SDG 12](#), [SDG 15](#), [SDG 16](#) and [SDG 17](#) show specific but not collective positions:
 - [SDG 2](#): University of Göttingen // Ghent University
 - [SDG 11](#): Comenius University Bratislava
 - [SDG 12](#): Uppsala University // Ghent University
 - [SDG 15](#): University of Göttingen
 - [SDG 16](#): Comenius University Bratislava
 - [SDG 17](#): Comenius University Bratislava

Figure 9 Collective and specific contribution to SDG per university based on ResPro

To sum up, [SDG 3](#) and [SDG 9](#) show similar specific positions across the 9 ENLIGHT universities on the SciPub as on the ResPro.

Similar specific positions according to the type of data should also be noted:

- SciPub Data: [SDG 10](#)
- ResPro data: [SDG 4](#), [SDG 7](#), [SDG 8](#), [SDG 13](#).

Figure 10 SDG' collective and specific contributions synthesis

C. Direct collaboration between ENLIGHT members to identify similarities related to R&I topic

Using FamPat and ResPro data allows analyzing direct collaborations between the universities of the ENLIGHT alliance.

- There are only 3 FamPat collaborations and they involve the University of Galway and the University of Groningen.
- On the ResPro data, collaborations pattern by university appears if we identify the universities with which each ENLIGHT University collaborates more than its average:
 - **University of the Basque Country collaborates more with:** University of Bordeaux // Comenius University Bratislava // Ghent University // University of Groningen // Uppsala University
 - **University of Bordeaux collaborates more with:** University of the Basque Country // Ghent University // University of Groningen // Uppsala University
 - **Comenius University Bratislava collaborates more with:** University of the Basque Country // University of Galway // University of Göttingen // University of Groningen // Uppsala University
 - **University of Galway collaborates more with:** University of the Basque Country // University of Bordeaux // Comenius University Bratislava // Ghent University // University of Göttingen // University of Groningen // University of Tartu // Uppsala University
 - **Ghent University collaborates more with:** University of Göttingen // University of Groningen // University of Tartu // Uppsala University
 - **University of Göttingen collaborates more with:** Ghent University // University of Groningen // University of Tartu // Uppsala University
 - **University of Groningen collaborates more with:** University of Bordeaux // Ghent University // University of Göttingen // Uppsala University
 - **University of Tartu collaborates more with:** Ghent University // University of Göttingen // Uppsala University
 - **Uppsala University collaborates more with:** Ghent University // University of Groningen // University of Tartu

	Collaborating with University of the Basque Country	Collaborating with University of Bordeaux	Collaborating with Comenius University Bratislava	Collaborating with University of Galway	Collaborating with Ghent University	Collaborating with University of Göttingen	Collaborating with University of Groningen	Collaborating with University of Tartu	Collaborating with Uppsala University
University of the Basque Country		0 / 7	0 / 5	0 / 3	0 / 9	0 / 1	0 / 5	0 / 4	0 / 6
University of Bordeaux	0 / 7		0 / 2	0 / 3	0 / 10	0 / 5	0 / 9	0 / 2	0 / 11
Comenius University Bratislava	0 / 5	0 / 2		0 / 4	0 / 3	0 / 4	0 / 4	0 / 2	0 / 4
University of Galway	0 / 3	0 / 3	0 / 4		0 / 8	0 / 2	3 / 6	0 / 6	0 / 12
Ghent University	0 / 9	0 / 10	0 / 3	0 / 8		0 / 11	0 / 12	0 / 14	0 / 22
University of Göttingen	0 / 1	0 / 5	0 / 4	0 / 2	0 / 11		0 / 10	0 / 12	0 / 10
University of Groningen	0 / 5	0 / 9	0 / 4	3 / 6	0 / 12	0 / 10		0 / 8	0 / 15
University of Tartu	0 / 4	0 / 2	0 / 2	0 / 6	0 / 14	0 / 12	0 / 8		0 / 27
Uppsala University	0 / 6	0 / 11	0 / 4	0 / 12	0 / 22	0 / 10	0 / 15	0 / 27	

Figure 11 Collaborations between ENLIGHT universities on FamPat / ResPro

On ResPro, collaboration above their individual average for the two concerned universities could be defined as a “significant collaboration”. Analyzing the SDG contribution on those “significant collaboration” helps to identify “significant thematic clusters” at the ENLIGHT scale.

Within the ENLIGHT alliance, these “significant thematic clusters” could be bases for working on the related topic as they are anchored on an existing “significant” collaboration between universities.

- [SDG 3](#): A significant thematic cluster on the SDG including Ghent University // University of Groningen // Uppsala University // University of Tartu
- [SDG 4](#): A significant thematic cluster on the SDG including Ghent University // University of Tartu
- [SDG 8](#): A significant thematic cluster on the SDG including University of Groningen // University of Bordeaux // Ghent University // University of Göttingen // Uppsala University
- [SDG 9](#): A significant thematic cluster on the SDG including University of Groningen // Ghent University // University of Bordeaux // University of Tartu
- [SDG 12](#): A significant thematic cluster on the SDG including University of Groningen // University of Bordeaux
- [SDG 13](#): A significant thematic cluster on the SDG including Ghent University // University of Groningen // University of Galway // Uppsala University
- [SDG 1](#), [SDG 2](#), [SDG 5](#), [SDG 6](#), [SDG 7](#), [SDG 10](#), [SDG 11](#), [SDG 14](#), [SDG 15](#), [SDG 16](#), [SDG 17](#): No significant thematic clusters were identified.

	Collaborating with University of the Basque Country	Collaborating with University of Bordeaux	Collaborating with Comenius University Bratislava	Collaborating with University of Galway	Collaborating with Ghent University	Collaborating with University of Göttingen	Collaborating with University of Groningen	Collaborating with University of Tartu	Collaborating with Uppsala University
University of the Basque Country		7 SDG 12 / SDG 9	5 NO SPECIFIC SDG	3 SDG 8 / SDG 9	9 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 7 / SDG 13	1 NO SPECIFIC SDG	5 SDG 8 / SDG 9	4 SDG 7	6 SDG 9
University of Bordeaux	7 SDG 12 / SDG 9		2 NO SPECIFIC SDG	3 NO SPECIFIC SDG	10 SDG 8 / SDG 9	5 SDG 8 / SDG 9	9 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 12	2 NO SPECIFIC SDG	11 SDG 8 / SDG 9
Comenius University Bratislava	5 NO SPECIFIC SDG	2 NO SPECIFIC SDG		4 SDG 8	3 NO SPECIFIC SDG	4 SDG 9	4 SDG 9	2 NO SPECIFIC SDG	4 NO SPECIFIC SDG
University of Galway	3 SDG 8 / SDG 9	3 NO SPECIFIC SDG	4 SDG 8		8 SDG 7 / SDG 9 / SDG 13 / SDG 12	2 NO SPECIFIC SDG	6 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 3	6 SDG 8 / SDG 9	12 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 13
Ghent University	9 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 7 / SDG 13	10 SDG 8 / SDG 9	3 NO SPECIFIC SDG	8 SDG 7 / SDG 9 / SDG 13 / SDG 12		11 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 4	12 SDG 3 / SDG 9 / SDG 13	14 SDG 4 / SDG 9	22 SDG 7 / SDG 9 / SDG 13
University of Göttingen	1 NO SPECIFIC SDG	5 SDG 8 / SDG 9	4 SDG 9	2 NO SPECIFIC SDG	11 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 4		10 SDG 8 / SDG 9	12 SDG 9	10 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 3
University of Groningen	5 SDG 8 / SDG 9	9 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 12	4 SDG 9	6 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 3	12 SDG 3 / SDG 9 / SDG 13	10 SDG 8 / SDG 9		8 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 12	15 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 12
University of Tartu	4 SDG 7	2 NO SPECIFIC SDG	2 NO SPECIFIC SDG	6 SDG 8 / SDG 9	14 SDG 4 / SDG 9	12 SDG 9	8 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 12		27 SDG 3 / SDG 9
Uppsala University	6 SDG 9	11 SDG 8 / SDG 9	4 NO SPECIFIC SDG	12 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 13	22 SDG 7 / SDG 9 / SDG 13	10 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 3	15 SDG 8 / SDG 9 / SDG 12	27 SDG 3 / SDG 9	

Figure 12 Collaborations between ENLIGHT universities on ResPro and associated SDG

<p>Number of ResPro in direct collaboration Most related SDGs</p>	<p>Collaboration above the average for the two related universities</p>
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D. Indirect collaborations *to identify similarities related to the existing R&I network*

FamPat and ResPro data are used to analyse the *indirect collaborations*.

These indirect collaborations rely on third-party organizations that are not members of the ENLIGHT alliance.

Although indirect, these type of collaborations as well as the organizations that are behind them can be relays of synergies to be fed or created directly for the members of the alliance in the desire to extend their influence.

For this analysis we also rely on the numbers of organisations characterized as *key partner / Transversal partner / Specific partner* [as defined in the methodology section](#).

By using the co-appearance information on data and with the help of network analysis tool (using [GEPHI](#)), 2 distinct configurations according to the 2 types of data used can be observed:

Partnership network based on FamPat

Figure 13 ENLIGHT collaboration network based on FamPat

The collaboration network based on the FamPat data (co-occurrence as applicants on the FamPat, cf. Figure 13) shows almost no direct collaborations between the universities of the ENLIGHT alliance (3 co-patents between the University of Galway and the University of Groningen).

However, the individual collaboration networks of each university of the ENLIGHT alliance are clearly identified and indirect collaborations also appears.

Three main conclusions regarding the need to create synergies:

1. No key partners appear based on FamPat.
2. *Transversal partners* represent 4% of all the partner on FamPat in these indirect collaborations and can be interesting relays to **create more direct relations between the members of the alliance.**

List of transversal partners on FamPat

Organization name – FPO/NFPO – Number of ENLIGHT universities with which the organization has existing collaborations

KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN - NFPO - 5 | BASF - FPO - 4 | CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS SPAIN - NFPO - 4 | INSERM FRANCE - NFPO - 3 | KONINKL - FPO - 3 | AGENCY SCIENCE TECH RES - NFPO - 3 | UNIVERSITY OF THE SCIENCES - NFPO - 3 | CNRS FRANCE - NFPO - 2 | GRONINGEN UNIVERSITY - NFPO - 2 | VIB VLAAMS INSTITUUT VOOR BIOTECHNOLOGIE BELGIUM - NFPO - 2 | NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY NUI IRELAND - NFPO - 2 | UMCG GRONINGEN NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 2 | CEA - FPO - 2 | THALES - FPO - 2 | VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL - NFPO - 2 | UNIVERSITY OF MONTPELLIER MONTPELLIER FRANCE - NFPO - 2 | BAYER - FPO - 2 | UNIVERSITY OF RENNES - NFPO - 2 | INRA FRANCE - NFPO - 2 | UNIVERSITY OF LILLE - NFPO - 2 | UNIVERSITY OF LILLE FRANCE - NFPO - 2 | UNIVERSITY OF BARCELONA BARCELONA SPAIN - NFPO - 2 | UNIV BRUXELLES - NFPO - 2 | PASTEUR INSTITUTE FRANCE - NFPO - 2 | UNIVERSITY OF NOTTINGHAM - NFPO - 2 | HEIDELBERG UNIVERSITY - NFPO - 2 | HEIDELBERG UNIVERSITY GERMANY - NFPO - 2 | HEALTH SCIENCE UNIVERSITY - NFPO - 2 | DELFT UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 2 | UNIVERSITY OF OREGON USA - NFPO - 2 | UNIVERSITY OF ZARAGOZA SPAIN - NFPO - 2 | JANSSEN - FPO - 2 | OREGON HEALTH SCIENCE UNIVERSITY - NFPO - 2 | INST NAT RECH INF AUTOMAT - NFPO - 2 | COLUMBIA UNIVERSITY USA - NFPO - 2 | UNIVERSITY OF LIVERPOOL UK - NFPO - 2 | ACADEMIC MEDICAL CENTER AMC AMSTERDAM NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 2 | COMPLUTENSE UNIVERSITY OF MADRID MADRID SPAIN - NFPO - 2 | DELFT UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY - NFPO - 2 | NOVARTIS - FPO - 2 | EINDHOVEN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY - NFPO - 2 | UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN UK - NFPO - 2 | UNIVERSITY OF CONNECTICUT USA - NFPO - 2 | ECOLE SUPERIEURE CHIMIE PARIS - NFPO - 2 | HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO - NFPO - 2 | BOCK HEALTHCARE GMBH - NFPO - 2 | FUND PRIVADA CTR REGULACIO GENOMICA CRG - NFPO - 2 | INST CATALANA RECERCA I ESTUDIS AVANCATS ICREA - NFPO - 2 | INST NAT POLYTECHNIQUE TOULOUSE - NFPO - 2 | MASSACHUSETTS INST TECHNOLOGY - NFPO - 2 | UNIV CALIFORNIA - NFPO - 2 | UNIV DEGLI STUDI MILANO - NFPO - 2 | UNIV MADRID POLITECNICA - NFPO - 2 | UNIV TEXAS - NFPO - 2

Figure 14 Transversal partners based on FamPat

- In addition, 96% of the categorized partners are *Specific partners*. This highlight the fact that, regarding FamPat, most universities have individual network of collaborators **containing organizations ready to engage in collaborations with universities** but are for the moment either unknown or never joined by the rest of the alliance members. Those individual network of collaborators should be investigated to enlarge the overall collaborations network.

Partnership network based on ResPro

Figure 155 ENLIGHT collaboration network based on ResPro

The network of collaboration based on the ResPro (participation to the same project, cf. Figure 15) shows a higher share of *key partners* (7%) and *transversal partners* (23%). These organizations could be relevant relays to initiate new collaborations in the future within the scope of ENLIGHT as they already show direct relations with the members of ENLIGHT.

List of Key partners on ResPro:

Organization name – FPO/NFPO – Number of ENLIGHT universities with which the organization has existing collaborations

KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN - NFPO - 9 | CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS SPAIN - NFPO - 9 | KONINKL - FPO - 9 | CNRS FRANCE - NFPO - 9 | CEA - FPO - 9 | VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF MONTPELLIER MONTPELLIER FRANCE - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF LILLE - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF LILLE FRANCE - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF BARCELONA BARCELONA SPAIN - NFPO - 9 | PASTEUR INSTITUTE FRANCE - NFPO - 9 | HEIDELBERG UNIVERSITY - NFPO - 9 | DELFT UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF ZARAGOZA SPAIN - NFPO - 9 | ACADEMIC MEDICAL CENTER AMC AMSTERDAM NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 9 | DELFT UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY - NFPO - 9 | EINDHOVEN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN UK - NFPO - 9 | HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO - NFPO - 9 | MAX PLANCK SOCIETY - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF ANTWERP BELGIUM - NFPO - 9 | AIX-MARSEILLE UNIVERSITY AIX-MARSEILLE FRANCE - NFPO - 9 | PARIS CITE UNIVERSITY PARIS FRANCE - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN - NFPO - 9 | TRINITY COLLEGE DUBLIN IRELAND - NFPO - 9 | UNIVs DUBLIN IRELAND - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF GRENOBLE - NFPO - 9 | GRENOBLE ALPES UNIVERSITY GRENOBLE FRANCE - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF TOULOUSE - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK IRELAND - NFPO - 9 | LEIDEN UNIVERSITY - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF VALENCIA VALENCIA SPAIN - NFPO - 9 | ECOLE NORMALE SUPERIEURE NO PRECISION FRANCE - NFPO - 9 |

PAUL SABATIER UNIVERSITY - NFPO - 9 | TOULOUSE III - PAUL SABATIER UNIVERSITY TOULOUSE FRANCE - NFPO - 9 | BIELEFELD UNIVERSITY GERMANY - NFPO - 9 | SORBONNE NOUVELLE UNIVERSITY PARIS 3 PARIS FRANCE - NFPO - 9 | SORBONNE UNIVERSITY PARIS FRANCE - NFPO - 9 | UTRECHT UNIVERSITY NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF LONDON - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE UK - NFPO - 9 | AARHUS UNIVERSITY DENMARK - NFPO - 9 | LEIDEN UNIVERSITY NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITE CATHOLIQUE DE LOUVAIN - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF ERLANGEN NUREMBERG GERMANY - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF GRANADA GRANADA SPAIN - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF PAVIA - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF EXETER UK - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NFPO - 9 | EINDHOVEN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF VALLADOLID VALLADOLID SPAIN - NFPO - 9 | UNIV OF STUTTGART - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF STUTTGART - NFPO - 9 | PHILIPS - FPO - 9 | UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE CATALUNYA - NFPO - 9 | EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY - NFPO - 9 | UNIV COLLEGE DUBLIN IRELAND - NFPO - 9 | KAROLINSKA UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL STOCKHOLM SWEDEN - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF AMSTERDAM - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF AMSTERDAM NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 9 | RABDOUD UNIVERSITY NIJMEGEN NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 9 | MAASTRICHT UNIVERSITY - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD UK - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON UK - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF OSLO - NFPO - 9 | MAASTRICHT UNIVERSITY NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 9 | CHARITE UNIVERSITÄTSMEDIZIN BERLIN GERMANY - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF HAMBURG GERMANY - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH UK - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER UK - NFPO - 9 | LINKÖPING UNIVERSITY SWEDEN - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM UK - NFPO - 9 | HELMHOLTZ CENTRE GERMANY - NFPO - 9 | DRESDEN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF BASEL - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF BRISTOL UK - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF WÜRZBURG GERMANY - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF INNSBRUCK AUSTRIA - NFPO - 9 | POLISH ACADEMY OF SCIENCES - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF GRAZ - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF SHEFFIELD UK - NFPO - 9 | QUEEN'S UNIVERSITY - NFPO - 9 | ASTRAZENeca - FPO - 9 | UNIV OF LORRAINE - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF JENA - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF DUSSELDORF GERMANY - NFPO - 9 | ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE SWITZERLAND - NFPO - 9 | CARDIFF UNIVERSITY UK - NFPO - 9 | QUEEN'S UNIVERSITY BELFAST UK - NFPO - 9 | QUEEN'S UNIVERSITY BELFAST - NFPO - 9 | VU UNIVERSITY MEDICAL CENTER AMSTERDAM NETHERLANDS - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF ZAGREB CROATIA - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF JENA GERMANY - NFPO - 9 | POMPEU FABRA UNIVERSITY BARCELONA SPAIN - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF SUSSEX UK - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN GERMANY - NFPO - 9 | AALBORG UNIVERSITY DENMARK - NFPO - 9 | PAUL SCHERRER INST - NFPO - 9 | BOSCH - FPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF ST. ANDREWS UK - NFPO - 9 | OPEN UNIVERSITY - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF ST ANDREWS - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITY OF CYPRUS - NFPO - 9 | FRAUNHOFER INSTITUTE - NFPO - 9 | DUBLIN CITY UNIV - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITA DI ROMA - NFPO - 9 | BULGARIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES - NFPO - 9 | INST SUPERIOR TECNICO - NFPO - 9 | GERMAN AEROSPACE CENTER DLR GERMANY - NFPO - 9 | NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF UKRAINE - NFPO - 9 | INST NAZIONALE DI FISICA NUCLEARE - NFPO - 9 | GRAZ UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITA CATTOLICA DEL SACRO CUORE ITALY - NFPO - 9 | CARLOS III UNIVERSITY OF MADRID - NFPO - 9 | NAT CTR SCIENTIFIC RES DEMOKRITOS - NFPO - 9 | CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE - NFPO - 9 | UNIV WIEN - NFPO - 9 | RUDER BOSKOVIC INST - NFPO - 9 | INST NAZIONALE DI ASTROFISICA - NFPO - 9 | POLITECNICO DI MILANO - NFPO - 9 | UNIV NACIONAL DE EDUCACION A DISTANCIA - NFPO - 9 | POLITECNICO DI TORINO ITALY - NFPO - 9 | INSERM - NFPO - 9 | KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET - NFPO - 9 | DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET - NFPO - 9 | EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH - NFPO - 9 | IMPERIAL COLLEGE AND MEDICINE - NFPO - 9 | KARLSRUHER INST FUER TECHNOLOGIE - NFPO - 9 | INST NAT RECHERCHE POUR L L ALIMENTATION L ENVIRONNEMENT - NFPO - 9 | KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLAN - NFPO - 9 | RHEINISCH WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN - NFPO - 9 | CHALMERS TEKNISKA HOGSKOLA AB - NFPO - 9 | FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JULICH GMBH - NFPO - 9 | STICHTING VU - NFPO - 9 | INST NAT RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE AUTOMATIQUE - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI - NFPO - 9 | IDRYMA TECHNOLOGIAS KAI EREVNAS - NFPO - 9 | TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN - NFPO - 9 | LUDWIG MAXIMILIANS UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN - NFPO - 9 | UNIV DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA - NFPO - 9 | BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CTR CTR NACIONAL SUPERCOMPUTACION - NFPO - 9 | ETHNIKO KAI KAPODISTRIAKO PANEPISTIMIO ATHINON - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERZITA KARLOVA - NFPO - 9 | STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET - NFPO - 9 | INST JOZEF STEFAN - NFPO - 9 | INTERUNIVERSITAIR ELECTRONICA CENTRUM - NFPO - 9 | JRC JOINT RES CTR EUROPEAN COMMISSION - NFPO - 9 | UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI - NFPO - 9 | MASARYKOVA UNIVERZITA - NFPO - 9 | TEKNOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS VTT OY - NFPO - 9 | ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS - NFPO - 9 | TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN - NFPO - 9 | STICHTING NEDERLANDSE WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK INSTITUTEN - NFPO - 9 | AALTO KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR - NFPO - 9 | CSC TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIKAN KESKUS OY - NFPO - 9 | SYDDANSK UNIVERSITET - NFPO - 9 | CINECA CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO - NFPO - 9 | ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION - NFPO - 9 | UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN - NFPO - 9 | INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK - NFPO - 9 | UNIV DEGLI STUDI DI FIRENZE - NFPO - 9 | POLITECHNIKA WARSZAWSKA - NFPO - 9 | TAMPEREEN KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR - NFPO - 9 | WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER - NFPO - 9 | FREIE UNIVERSITAET BERLIN - NFPO - 9 | ILMATIETEEN LAITOS - NFPO - 9 | OESTERREICHISCHE AKADEMIE WISSENSCHAFTEN - NFPO - 9 | UNIWERSYTET JAGIELLONSKI - NFPO - 9 | AKADEMIA GORNICZO HUTNICZA IM STANISLAWA STASZICA W KRAKOWIE - NFPO - 9 | PANEPISTIMIO IOANNINON - NFPO - 9 | CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE - NFPO - 9 | UNIV DE SEVILLA - NFPO - 9 | VETENSKAPSRADET SWEDISH RES - NFPO - 9 | PANEPISTIMIO THESSALIAS - NFPO - 9 |

Figure 16 Key partners based on ResPro

IV. INDIVIDUAL PROFILES FOR ENLIGHT MEMBERS

Individual profiles for each university have been created based on the collected and processed data. In consequence, these profiles are impacted by the choices and limits exposed in the methodological section. These implications should be considered to understand the scope of individual profiles.

University of the Basque Country
University of Bordeaux
Comenius University Bratislava
University of Galway
Ghent University
University of Göttingen
University of Groningen
University of Tartu
Uppsala University

A. University of the Basque Country

310 FamPat - 21,200 SciPub – 331 ResPro

Volume of collected data

- University of the Basque Country has a steady and increasing activity regarding SciPub and ResPro.
- The activity in terms of FamPat appears to be more discontinuous.
- UPV/EHU has a notable contribution to [SDG 3](#), [SDG 9](#) and [SDG 10](#) regardless of the type of data and also contribute significantly to [SDG 13](#) regarding ResPro.
- University of the Basque Country has a steady and increasing activity regarding SciPub and ResPro.
- The activity in terms of FamPat appears to be more discontinuous.
- FamPat network shows 20% of partners are FPOs (18 FPOs out of 111 partners), showing relatively strong ecosystem related to FPOs.
- Recent FPOs partners including:
 - FamPat (since 2019): IKERCHEM S | DOMINION PHARMAKINE S L | AIDELOS SRL LAB | ENERGY ENVIRONMENT CONSULTING S L | IBM
 - SciPub (since 2019): CIDETEC DONOSTIA SPAIN | ISGLOBAL | IBM | OWL METABOLOMICS DERIO SPAIN | BASF
 - ResPro (since 2019): CEA | TNO | BASF | SINTEF | ACCIONA

B. University of Bordeaux

680 FamPat - 25,157 SciPub - 208 ResPro

Volume of collected data

- University of Bordeaux has a steady and increasing activity in terms of FamPat, SciPub and ResPro.
- Its contribution to [SDG 3](#) is important regardless of the S&T data.
- The recent growing topics are also strongly connected to *health* and *medical science*.
- University of Bordeaux has a steady and increasing activity in terms of FamPat, SciPub and ResPro.
- Its contribution to [SDG 3](#) is important regardless of the S&T data.
- The recent growing topics are also
- University of Bordeaux has a large network of partners, regardless of the S&T data.
- Strongly connected to the national network of research institution we also find numerous connexions with FPO including:
 - FamPat (since 2019): SAFRAN | THALES | CEA | ARKEMA | PSA AUTOMOBILES SA
 - SciPub (since 2019): CEA | EDF | JANSSEN | NOVARTIS | HOFFMANN LA ROCHE
 - ResPro (since 2019): CEA | STMICROELECTRONICS | KONINKL |

C. Comenius University Bratislava

112 FamPat - 7,795 SciPub – 57 ResPro

Volume of collected data

- Discontinuous activity regarding FamPat and ResPro but increasing activity regarding SciPub.
- Recent and important topics of interest seems connected to *Medicine* and *Biology*.
- Great contribution made to [SDG 3](#) and [SDG 9](#) and [SDG 10](#).
- Discontinuous activity regarding FamPat and ResPro but increasing activity regarding SciPub.
- Recent and important topics of interest seems connected to *Medicine* and *Dis...*
- ResPro network shows wide set of collaborators on the 57 ResPro but few FPOs involved.
- This also appears regarding the FamPat network that does not include any FPOs.
- Recent FPOs partners including:
- No recent FPOs collaborations on FamPat.
- SciPub (since 2019): CEA | ST MICHAEL S GAA SLIGO | ASTRAZENECA | NATURALIS | PFIZER
- ResPro (since 2019): CEA | TNO | BOSCH | PHILIPS | MATIS OHF | VOLKSWAGEN | ILLUMINA | ABB

D. University of Galway

260 FamPat - 9,747 SciPub – 338 ResPro

Volume of collected data

- NUI Galway has a steady and increasing activity in terms of FamPat, SciPub and ResPro.
- Although on the SciPub the [SDG 3](#) is by far the one with the greatest contribution, we note significant contributions and more diversified on the ResPro: [SDG 1](#), [SDG 3](#), [SDG 4](#), [SDG 7](#), [SDG 8](#), [SDG 9](#).
- Recent important topics regarding SciPub are connected to *health and medical science*.
- NUI Galway has a steady and increasing activity in terms of FamPat, SciPub and ResPro.
- Recent FPOs partners including:
 - No recent FPOs collaborations on FamPat.
 - SciPub (since 2019): TEAGASC | CERENOVUS GALWAY IRELAND | JANSSEN | LAWSON | BAYER
 - ResPro (since 2019): CEA | TEAGASC | ATOS | KONINKL | JOHNSON MATTHEY
- Recent FPOs partners including:
 - No recent FPOs collaborations on FamPat.
 - SciPub (since 2019): TEAGASC | CERENOVUS GALWAY IRELAND | JANSSEN | LAWSON | BAYER

E. Ghent University

1,018 FamPat – 35,509 SciPub - 644 ResPro

Volume of collected data

- UGent has an strong S&T data portfolio which shows a constant and important growth in the last years.
- UGent strongly contributes to almost all the SDGs but more specifically we can note the contribution made to [SDG 3](#), [SDG 7](#), [SDG 9](#) and [SDG 12](#), on ResPro.
- Concerning SciPub, the contributions to, [SDG 2](#), [SDG 3](#), [SDG 4](#), [SDG 9](#), [SDG 10](#), [SDG 13](#) and [SDG 15](#) are noticeable.
- UGent has an strong S&T data portfolio which shows a constant and important growth in the last years.
- UGent strongly contributes to almost all
- The FamPat networks is one of the most developed in terms of partners involved (in part because it is the alliance's largest FamPat portfolio): 544 partners on FamPat / 20% of them qualify as FPOs.
- Recent FPOs partners including:
 - FampPat (since 2019): IMEC | ORIONIS | BIOSCIENCE | AD | RECTICEL | COLGATE PALMOLIVE
 - SciPub (since 2019): IMEC | JANSSEN | CEA | SANOFI | LABORATORIES
 - ResPro (since 2019): CEA | IBM | KONINKL | TEAGASC | DELL

F. University of Göttingen

260 FamPat – 24,543 SciPub – 244 ResPro*

Volume of collected data - *UGOE profile regarding ResPro also integrate UMG

- University of Göttingen has a steady and increasing activity regarding SciPub and ResPro.
- The activity in terms of FamPat seems to be more discontinuous.
- The contribution to [SDG 3](#), [SDG 2](#), [SDG 9](#), [SDG 10](#), [SDG 13](#) and [SDG 15](#) is notable on SciPub.
- While regarding the contributions to the SDG made by ResPro, [SDG 9](#) is by far the most important.
- University of Göttingen has a steady and increasing activity regarding SciPub and ResPro.
- Although 20% of partners in FamPat are FPOs, there are few of them when considering the recent years (3 FPOs partner since 2019).
- Recent FPOs partners including:
 - SciPub (since 2019): PRAXIS | NOVARTIS | BOSCH | K S KALI GMBH KASSEL GERMANY | CHRONIX BIOMEDICAL GOTTINGEN GERMANY
 - ResPro (since 2019): KONINKL | NOVARTIS
- Although 20% of partners in FamPat are FPOs, there are few of them when considering the recent years (3 FPOs partner since 2019).

G. University of Groningen

352 FamPat – 38,496 SciPub - 604 ResPro

Volume of collected data

- University of Groningen has a steady and increasing activity regarding SciPub and ResPro.
- The activity in terms of FamPat seems to be more discontinuous.
- High contribution to [SDG 3](#) and [SDG 9](#) and [SDG 10](#) regardless of the S&T data.
- Also, recent fields of study in SciPub are strongly connected to *medical science*.
- University of Groningen has a steady and increasing activity regarding SciPub and ResPro.
- The activity in terms of FamPat seems to be more discontinuous.
- Recent FPOs partners including:
 - FampPat (since 2019): DSM | SULFATEQ | BASF | SANKO TEKSTIL ISLETMELERI SAN VE TIC AS | ZORG INNOVATIES NEDERLAND B V
 - SciPub (since 2019): BOSCH | ASTRAZENECA | NOVARTIS | JANSSEN | HLTH
 - ResPro (since 2019): CEA | IBM | KONINKL | THALES | STMICROELECTRONICS
- Recent FPOs partners including:
 - FampPat (since 2019): DSM | SULFATEQ | BASF | SANKO TEKSTIL ISLETMELERI

H. University of Tartu

96 FamPat – 8,381 SciPub - 283 ResPro

Volume of collected data

- University of Tartu has a steady and increasing activity regarding SciPub and ResPro.
- The activity in terms of FamPat seems to be more discontinuous.
- Apart from [SDG 3](#) which concentrates by far the most contribution concerning SciPub. The contributions made to [SDG 9](#), [SDG 10](#), [SDG 13](#) and [SDG 15](#) is noticeable.
- Regarding the ResPro, a more specific contribution to [SDG 3](#), [SDG 4](#), [SDG 8](#) and [SDG 9](#) appears.
- Very few FPOs in the FamPat networks.
- Most of FPOs are related to ResPro and Sci Pub.
- Recent FPOs partners including:
 - SciPub (since 2019): SYNLAB GROUP | KAISER PERMANENTE | NOVARTIS | ISGLOBAL | GSK
 - ResPro (since 2019): CEA | THALES | DELL | LEONARDO | SINTEF
- Very few FPOs in the FamPat networks.
- Most of FPOs are related to ResPro and Sci Pub.
- Recent FPOs partners including:

I. Uppsala University

7 FamPat – 40,807 SciPub - 539 ResPro

Volume of collected data

- Uppsala University has a specific situation regarding the collected S&T data as it does not have related FamPat because of internal rules of attribution of patents.
- Apart from that, Uppsala University has one of the most important SciPub and ResPro S&T data portfolio.
- The contribution to the SDGs is important but more specific concerning [SDG 3](#), [SDG 9](#), [SDG 10](#), [SDG 13](#), [SDG 15](#) and [SDG 2](#) on SciPub.
- From the ResPro, an important specific contribution concerning [SDG 3](#), [SDG 9](#), [SDG 7](#) and [SDG 13](#) can be noted.
- On SciPub, Uppsala University has strong links to FPOs ecosystem.
- Recent FPOs partners including:
 - SciPub (since 2019): ASTRAZENECA | KATHMANDU | NOVARTIS | GSK | MERCK
 - ResPro (since 2019): CEA | JANSSEN | PFIZER | KONINKL | NOVARTIS
- On SciPub, Uppsala University has strong links to FPOs ecosystem.
- Recent FPOs partners including:
 - SciPub (since 2019): ASTRAZENECA | KATHMANDU | NOVARTIS | GSK | MERCK

APPENDIX

This report highlights key facts based on statistical analysis of S&T data associated with ENLIGHT alliance universities.

Although it highlights the most important results, it relies on work that was carried out within the scope of all the collected data.

The main collected and processed data are available in this appendix and should be considered also as elements to help identify synergies between the universities in the scope of complementary investigations.

A. Global S&T data

The 3 collected and processed S&T data sets have been shared with the ENLIGHT partners (via SharePoint, restricted access):

- Global FamPat Data are available [here](#)
- Global SciPub Data are available [here](#)
- Global ResPro Data are available [here](#)

B. Global organization characterization data

The list of organizations associated with the 3 S&T datasets processed is available as restricted access document. It includes the characterization of the organizations as well as the data associated with the collaborations with the universities of the ENLIGHT alliance.

- Organization characterization data is available [here](#).

C. Individual data per university

Additional data to the SDGs to analyse topics at the level of the 9 universities and the ENLIGHT alliance:

- FamPat: “Topics” extracted for each university of the ENLIGHT alliance.
- SciPub: “Fields of Study” for ENLIGHT alliance university.
- ResPro: “EuroSciVoc” for each ENLIGHT alliance university.
- University topics’ extraction data is available [here](#).